

A. Zero-shot System Prompt

For zero-shot multimodal models, we used the following system prompt to obtain phoneme sequences. The variable `vocab_lines` was populated from the public Arabic phoneme vocabulary.²

Zero-shot system prompt

You are a professional Speech-Language Pathologist (SLP) specializing in Arabic phonology, expert in phoneme extraction.

You will be given an Arabic audio recording. Transcribe it as a sequence of phonemes using ONLY the symbols from the vocabulary below.

Vocabulary
(symbol -> IPA -> letter + example):
{vocab_lines}

Rules:

- Must understand the audio, then break it down to phoneme level keeping exactly what is pronounced.
- Use ONLY the symbols listed above (left-hand column).
- Separate each phoneme with a single space.
- Output must be a JSON object with a single key "phonemes" whose value is the space-separated phoneme sequence.
- Do NOT include Arabic text, explanations, or any extra fields.
- Example output:
{ "phonemes": "< a l b aa b u" }

Now extract the accurate phonemes from the provided audio.

B. Evaluation Sample Curation

The 40-sample evaluation set was curated to represent diverse pronunciation conditions encountered in clinical Arabic speech assessment. Samples were drawn from five publicly available datasets: IqraEval/Iqra_train³ (20 samples), Quran Recitation Errors⁴ (10), Common Voice 18 Arabic⁵ (5), Arabic Quran ASR⁶ (3), and Arabic Quranic ASR⁷ (2).

The set was balanced along two axes: **content type** (25 non-Quranic, 15 Quranic) and **pronunciation quality** (32 correct, 8 with deliberate mispronunciations). Samples span 30 unique speakers and range from 7.0 to 24.4 s in duration (mean 10.2 s). All reference texts are fully diacritized Arabic, enabling

²huggingface.co/spaces/IqraEval/ArabicPhoneme

³https://huggingface.co/datasets/IqraEval/Iqra_train

⁴<https://huggingface.co/datasets/sobolev210/quran-recitation-errors>

⁵<https://huggingface.co/datasets/MohamedRashad/common-voice-18-arabic>

⁶<https://huggingface.co/datasets/Sabri12blm/Arabic-Quran-ASR-dataset>

⁷https://huggingface.co/datasets/Sadique5/arabic_quranic_asr

deterministic phoneme generation. Audio quality was verified via RMS loudness, clipping ratio, and spectral flatness checks.

C. Evaluation Metrics

In this study, we employ several standard metrics to evaluate both phoneme-level recognition performance and agreement between human raters and automated systems. This section provides detailed definitions and formulas for each metric.

Phoneme Error Rate (PER). A commonly used metric to quantify the performance of automatic phoneme recognition systems. PER measures the proportion of incorrectly predicted phonemes relative to the total number of phonemes in the reference transcription. It is defined as:

$$\text{PER} = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

where:

- S = number of substitutions,
- D = number of deletions,
- I = number of insertions,
- N = total number of phonemes in the reference.

A lower PER indicates better phoneme recognition performance.

Real-Time Factor (RTF). Measures the computational efficiency of an automatic speech recognition (ASR) system. It is defined as the ratio of the time taken by the model to process an audio signal to the actual duration of the audio:

$$\text{RTF} = \frac{T_{\text{process}}}{T_{\text{audio}}} \quad (5)$$

where T_{process} is the time required for inference and T_{audio} is the duration of the audio input. An $\text{RTF} < 1$ indicates real-time processing capability.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC). Measures the linear correlation between two continuous variables. For two sets of ratings $X = \{x_i\}$ and $Y = \{y_i\}$, PCC is computed as:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (6)$$

where \bar{x} and \bar{y} denote the mean values of X and Y . PCC values range from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to $+1$ (perfect positive correlation).

Spearman Correlation Coefficient (SCC). A non-parametric measure of rank correlation. It assesses the monotonic relationship between two variables and is calculated as:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad (7)$$

where d_i is the difference between the ranks of the i -th elements in the two variables, and n is the number of observations.

Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC). Quantifies the consistency or agreement of measurements made by multiple raters on the same subjects. For the ICC(2,1) model used in this study, which is based on a two-way random-effects model for single measurements, it is defined as:

$$\text{ICC}(2,1) = \frac{MS_B - MS_W}{MS_B + (k - 1)MS_W + k(MS_R - MS_W)/n} \quad (8)$$

where:

- MS_B = mean square between subjects,

- MS_W = mean square within subjects (error),
- MS_R = mean square between raters,
- k = number of raters,
- n = number of subjects.

ICC values range from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (perfect agreement).

Mean Absolute Error (MAE). Measures the average magnitude of errors between predicted and reference values, without considering their direction:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (9)$$

where y_i is the reference score and \hat{y}_i is the predicted score.

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). Provides a measure of the magnitude of error that penalizes larger deviations more than MAE:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (10)$$

Exact and ± 1 Accuracy. Exact accuracy is the percentage of predictions that exactly match the reference score:

$$\text{Exact (\%)} = \frac{\# \text{ exact matches}}{n} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

± 1 accuracy allows predictions within one unit of the reference as correct:

$$\pm 1 (\%) = \frac{\# \text{ predictions within 1 of reference}}{n} \times 100 \quad (12)$$

These metrics collectively provide a comprehensive assessment of both phoneme-level recognition accuracy and agreement with human expert raters.